

COMBINED MULTI-SCALE SIMULATIONS IN FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A coupled experimental-computational micromechanical framework has been developed to determine mechanical properties of a fiber-reinforced composite lamina, namely longitudinal compressive strength and longitudinal tensile strength. This methodology includes experimental characterization of matrix and interface, combined with numerical simulations of a Representative Volume Element (RVE) of the real microstructure, reproducing fiber diameters and spatial distribution. The interface decohesion mechanism is simulated using cohesive elements. A pressure dependent, elasto-plastic model is employed to capture matrix shear yielding. Tensile and compression damage are also independently included in the matrix constitutive equation. Numerical predictions were compared with experimental results available in the literature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) are nowadays extensively used in applications where outstanding mechanical properties are necessary in combination with weight savings. Predicting mechanical properties and failure mechanisms in CFRP has become one of the most active areas in research activities related to material science. The influence of the microstructure and the mechanisms of deformation and fracture of the constituents in the mechanical properties of CFRP has been proven by many authors during recent years. Nevertheless, reliable and accurate failure criteria for composite materials are still under investigation. Nowadays, Computational Micromechanics has stood out as a powerful tool to predict these physical mechanisms as well as the mechanical properties, in good agreement with experimental data.

The traditional way to tackle the problem is through extensive and costly experimental programs which involve material characterization through different levels up to the final global structure. Material testing begins at the ply coupon level and a tremendous effort is needed in order to test materials under tension, compression and shear, to fully certify the different ply properties. Moreover, additional tests might be required under different ageing and environmental conditions, delaying the experimental program in months and years until final material certification.

In this work, a coupled experimental-computational micromechanical framework has been developed to determine matrix dependent mechanical properties of the composite, namely transversal compressive strength, transversal tensile strength and in-plane shear strength. This methodology includes experimental characterization of matrix and interface, combined with numerical simulations of a *Representative Volume Element* RVE.

Experimental Micromechanics is based on instrumented indentation at the fiber/matrix scale. The properties obtained at this level, the *in-situ* properties of the matrix and fiber/matrix interface, are directly used as material data for a computational micromechanics analysis. In addition, detailed

information of the microstructure, such as fiber diameter distribution, volume fraction, fiber clusters and resin pockets, is captured and included in the computational model by means of a traditional RVE approach [15,16].

In this work, the micromechanical experiments required by the constitutive equations used in the RVE simulations are described in first place. Next, the computational strategies employed in both tension and compression simulations are explained in detail. Finally, results are compared to the literature available data.

2 EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION OF PLY CONSTITUENTS

The material used in this work is a Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) matrix composite unidirectional laminate with aeronautical grade, obtained from Hexcel AS4/8552 prepregs. This is a well-known composite material and most of its properties can be found in the literature or are directly provided by the supplier. However, in order to validate both computational and experimental techniques presented in this work, some of them, such as matrix elastic modulus, matrix compressive strength and fiber/matrix interface strength have been derived by means of instrumented nanoindentation techniques on the intra-ply matrix rich regions. Following the in-situ methodology developed by Rodriguez [12,13] for materials that present a cohesive-frictional behavior, elastic and plastic properties can be found combining the micromechanical tests results with master curves obtained from finite element analysis of the indentation process.

2.1 Matrix nanoindentation tests

Nanoindentation tests were performed on the 8552 epoxy resin at two different environmental conditions: RT/DRY (Room Temperature; Dry atmosphere) and 70/85 (Temperature, 70 °C; Moisture, 85%). Indentation experiments were conducted using a Hysitron TI 950 TriboIndenter equipped with a Berkovich tip (pyramidal indenter). AS4/8552 samples were previously cut using a diamond saw and polished perpendicular-to-the-fiber cross section in order to prepare them for the indentation.

Regarding matrix characterization under HOT/WET conditions, the samples were dried into a stove, AFA 200/150 Dycometal furnace, and weighted prior to be introduced in a climatic chamber, CCK-0/125 Dycometal model, at the required conditions (70/85). In order to speed up the process, the size of the samples was significantly small compared to standard travelers (manufactured according to DIN EN2823) but large enough to carry out all the instrumented indentations.

The weight of each sample was measured by means of a AG245 Mettler Toledo balance at different time intervals to check water absorption until saturation conditions were achieved (the difference between two consecutive measurement is below some specific threshold according to the EN2823 standard). At this point, several samples were taken out of the climatic chamber and used in the nanoindenter apparatus.

As the temperature of the samples fell down very fast when they were taken out of the climatic chamber, a special loading module equipped with a heating device was used instead of the ordinary one. The tip was also a Berkovich one. Once the required temperature was reached on the surface of the sample, indentations were performed. Therefore, tests were carried out under the specific HOT/WET environmental conditions.

The results of the indentation tests on the 8552 epoxy resin in the afore mentioned conditions (RT/DRY and 70/85) are summarized in Table 1. Regarding the Young modulus, the value obtained from nanoindentation for RT/DRY is in good agreement with the one provided by the supplier ($E = 4670$ MPa). Nevertheless, there is a small discrepancy between both values that may come from two different sources, namely the estimation of the contact area and the high fiber volume fraction of the composite.

Condition	H_{ap} [Pa]	W_e / W_t	H_{ap} / σ_{yc}	β	σ_{yc} [Pa]	E [Pa]
RT/DRY	$(297 \pm 30) \cdot 1e6$	0.5477	1.69	29°	$(176 \pm 17) \cdot 1e6$	$(5.07 \pm 0.3) \cdot 1e9$
HOT/WET	$(275 \pm 16) \cdot 1e6$	0.5093	1.81	29°	$(152 \pm 8) \cdot 1e6$	$(4.28 \pm 0.2) \cdot 1e9$

Table 1. Results of AS4/8552 push-in tests under RT/DRY and HOT/WET conditions.

2.2 Fiber/Matrix interface push-in tests

In this work, the push-in technique has been chosen in order to calculate the interfacial shear strength following the methodology developed by Rodríguez [13]. All the push-in tests were performed using a Hysitron TI 950 TriboIndenter equipped with a 5 μ m diameter flat punch tip. According to Rodríguez [13] a 3D finite element model of the push-in test, taking into account real properties of the fibers and their local packing, can be used to determine the interfacial strength. The relationship obtained from the FEM model, is used to calculate the interfacial strength by means of the critical shear derived from the real push-in tests.

A total of fifteen *push-in* tests were carried out for each environmental condition (RT/DRY and HOT/WET). The average values are gathered in Table 2. It can be observed how the interfacial strength decreases under HOT/WET conditions. Nevertheless, one consideration must be taken into account, the *push-in* tests on the conditioned samples were carried out at room temperature, so the interfacial strength can decrease even more when increasing the temperature of the test [13].

Condition	S_0 [N/m]	P_{crit} [N]	τ_{crit} [Pa]	τ_d [Pa]
RT/DRY	$(105.24 \pm 2.71) \cdot 1e3$	0.062495 ± 0.003750	$(30.76 \pm 1.88) \cdot 1e6$	$(63.77 \pm 2.64) \cdot 1e6$
HOT/WET	$(119.71 \pm 7.93) \cdot 1e3$	0.052261 ± 0.003814	$(29.25 \pm 1.65) \cdot 1e6$	$(51.58 \pm 2.72) \cdot 1e6$

Table 2. Results of AS4/8552 push-in tests under RT/DRY and HOT/WET conditions.

2.3 AS4/8552 fiber distribution analysis

Following the methodology developed by Vaughan[16], the material cross section is observed and the microstructure is analyzed using an image processing program. Fibers clusters and matrix rich regions are observed. (Figure 1). Distribution of diameters and distances to the neighboring fibers are measured and fitted by statistical functions in order to generate a virtual microstructure statistically equivalent to the real one (Table 3).

Figure 1. AS4/8552 micrograph after being processed using the *ImageJ* open source software.

Parameter	Fiber diameter [m]	1st neighbor distance [m]	2nd neighbor distance [m]
Mean	7.2476e-6	7.456936e-6	7.84089e-6
Std. deviation	0.41185e-6	0.34589e-6	0.62662e-6

Table 3. Statistical distribution parameters required to generate a virtual microstructure statistically equivalent to a real one

3 COMPUTATIONAL MICROMECHANICS

In this work, the finite element method is used to simulate the behavior of the AS4/8552 composite unidirectional ply. Material properties derived using nanoindentation and push-in techniques are used as an input of the constitutive equations of matrix and interface. Longitudinal tension strength, X_T , and longitudinal compression strength, X_C , are predicted using the same set of properties. Residual thermal stresses and periodic boundary conditions have been taken into account.

In previous work [9], this strategy was used to predict the transverse and shear properties of the AS4/8552 ply. Herein, it is used to predict the longitudinal ones. This simulation methodology and constitutive equations have been developed using a commercial finite element software ABAQUS®/Standard.

3.1 Material modeling and microstructure generation

The matrix non-linear behavior was modeled using a coupled damage-plasticity constitutive equation in order to handle the non-linearity due to plasticity in the matrix under compressive stress states and the quasi-brittle behavior under tensile loads. Among the different choices available in ABAQUS®/Standard, the *Concrete Damaged Plasticity* model stands out as one of the most suitable ones in order to represent the quasi-brittle behavior of the epoxy matrix [2].

The AS4 carbon fibers are modeled in this work as linear, elastic and transversally isotropic solids. The fiber/matrix interface is represented using a cohesive surface interaction. The interfacial strength calculated by means of the push-in tests is introduced here. A quadratic criterion is used to predict delamination initiation. Damage evolution is simulated using a mixed mode behavior. The *Mode I* and *Mode II* fracture energies are set equal to the values used by Lopes et al. [6]. The properties employed in the simulations are gathered in Table 4.

The microstructure of the composite is idealized as a dispersion of cylinders which represents the shape of the fibers. In this work two well-known algorithms, namely, the *Random Sequential Adsorption* (RSA) algorithm [15] and the *Nearest Neighbor Algorithm* (NNA)[16] were modified in order to generate a virtual three dimensional RVE (Figure 2). The fibers distribution is generated according to the information extracted from real micrographs of the AS4/8552 material (fiber radius, volume fraction, etc.).

8552 Epoxy matrix properties (RT/DRY)							
ρ [Kg/m ³]	E[Pa]	ν	X^T [Pa]	β	σ_{yc} [Pa]	G_{IC} [J/m ²]	α [K ⁻¹]
1301	5.07e9	0.35	121e6	29°	176e6	100	52e-6
AS4 Carbon fiber properties							
ρ [Kg/m ³]	E_1 [Pa]	E_2 [Pa]	G_{12} [Pa]	G_{23} [Pa]	ν_{12} [Pa]	α_1 [K ⁻¹]	α_2 [K ⁻¹]
1790	231e9	12.97e9	11.28e9	4.45e9	0.3	-0.63e-6	7.2e-6
AS4/8552 interface properties (RT/DRY)							
σ_1 [Pa]	τ_2 [Pa]	τ_3 [Pa]	G_{IC} [J/m ²]	G_{IIC} [J/m ²]	G_{IIIC} [J/m ²]		
42e6	63e6	63e6	280	790	790		

Table 4. Matrix, fibers and interface properties used in the simulations.

Figure 2. Virtual microstructures, generated using the NNA(left) and RSA(right) algorithms.

3.2 Longitudinal tensile loading

As it was mentioned before, the AS4 carbon fibers are modeled in this work as linear, elastic and transversally isotropic solids. However, fracture planes are introduced randomly to limit the fiber strength under tensile loads. A cohesive surface interaction is introduced here in order to reproduce the fiber fracture. The maximum stress criterion is used in this case to represent the damage initiation. Damage evolution is taken into account by means of a linear energy-based softening law[14]. In order to increase the accuracy of the model, the cohesive strength between the different fiber fracture planes is reproduced using the Weibull distribution function according to the experimental data obtained by Lopes et al. [7]. Fiber fracture properties are summarize in Table 5.

AS4 Carbon fiber fracture properties				
X_T	x	σ_0 [Pa]	m	G_{IC} [J/m ²]
$\sigma_0(-\log x)^{1/m}$	$x \in (0,1)$	4.43e9	8.86	10

Table 5. AS4 cohesive interaction strength and toughness according to Weibull distribution parameters

The virtual test process is represented in 4 steps (Figure 3 and Figure 4). When the ply is loaded in tension, fibers start to absorb the load uniformly until the weakest fiber-fiber interface fails. At this point, a stress redistribution is produced and the resultant stress concentration is absorbed by the neighboring fibers (A and B). More fractures planes fail successively reaching a saturation value leading to the catastrophic failure of the microstructure (C and D).

Figure 3. Evolution of equivalent von Mises stress in the RVE under longitudinal tension.

Figure 4. Stress-strain curve corresponding to the longitudinal tension of the TVE. A, B, C and D represents the loading states shown in Figure 3.

3.3 Longitudinal compressive loading

Unidirectional compression is a complex topic not perfectly solved in the literature as different failure mechanisms can occur at different scales of observation. Typically, unidirectional compression of high strength carbon composites is controlled by fiber kinking at the lower scale but strongly affected by waviness, imperfections, fiber misalignment, etc, arising from the manufacturing process.

To date, several analytical models are available in the literature providing good approximation to the available experimental data. These models can deal with elasto-plastic materials and are able to predict the kink band width and inclination [1,10,11]. In addition, some authors have developed 2D FEM models in order to provide a better understanding of the initiation and propagation phenomena of kink bands[4,11].

In this work , the same strategy followed by Gutkin et al. [3] to simulate the fiber kinking was adopted. A 2D model containing one sinusoidal fiber is carried out. Periodic boundary conditions are applied in the direction perpendicular to the fiber (Figure 5). Cohesive elements (COH2D4) are introduced in the fiber/matrix interface to simulate debonding.

Figure 5. 2D FEM model containing one sinusoidal fiber to study the kink band phenomenon

During the longitudinal compression, the fiber deforms in the elastic regime until a critical load value required to trigger local buckling is reached. At this point, we can observe a strong decrease in the stress-strain curve. During this unloading, the matrix deforms under plastic regime and the kink band is formed. If further compression is applied, the kink-band starts broadening until reaching a constant stress value. At this point, fiber breakage should take place. However, as no fiber failure criterion has been defined, the fiber deforms elastically.

In order to check the influence of the initial fiber misalignment, ϕ_0 , six different fibers have been submitted for analysis. The stress-strain curves, for RT/DRY conditions, are plotted in Figure 6 . The compressive strength, for RT/DRY and HOT/WET conditions are gathered in Table 6. The relationship between the maximum load and the initial fiber misalignment is plotted in Figure 7 .

Regarding the elastic modulus the mean value obtained is $E = 182$ GPa for both RT/DRY and HOT/WET conditions.

	Initial fiber misalignment , ϕ_0 (°)					
	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
X_C (RT/DRY)	2038 MPa	1621 MPa	1342 MPa	1145 MPa	1000 MPa	878 MPa
X_C (HOT/WET)	1860 MPa	1453 MPa	1184 MPa	999 MPa	858 MPa	736 MPa

Table 6. Compressive strength according to initial fiber misalignment

Figure 6. Stress-strain curves of AS4/8552 longitudinal compression, under RT/DRY condition, for different initial fiber misalignment

Figure 7. AS4/8552 longitudinal compressive strength against initial fiber misalignment, for RT/DRY and HOT/WET conditions

The 2D FEM model is able to reproduce the effect of the fiber misalignment in the compression strength. In addition, the influence of both non-linear matrix and fiber-matrix interface is captured as it can be seen in Figure 7 .

In order to summarize, the predicted values for the two fiber-dependent ply strengths (longitudinal tension strength, X_T and longitudinal compression strength, X_C) are gathered and compared with the values found in the literature [8] for RT/DRY and HOT/WET conditions (Table 7).

	X_T (RT/DRY)	X_C (RT/DRY)	X_T (HOT/WET)	X_C (HOT/WET)
Literature	2061-2207 MPa	1484-1531 MPa	2061-2207 MPa	1100 MPa
Predicted	2160 MPa	1340-1621 MPa	2160 MPa	1183-1453 MPa

Table 7. Longitudinal ply strength values for AS4/8552 under RT/DRY and HOT/WET conditions

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, longitudinal tensile properties have been predicted using a 3D FEM model that takes into account the real fiber distribution (fiber packing, clusters, matrix rich regions, etc. can also be taken into account). The obtained elastic modulus and longitudinal strength compare well with experimental values in the available literature [8].

Regarding the longitudinal compression properties, a 2D FEM model has been used to calculate the influence of the geometrical imperfections (initial fiber misalignment angle) in the compression strength. The effect of matrix elasto-plastic and fiber-matrix interface is also taken into account.

All the simulations were carried out using the commercial software ABAQUS®/Standard. Neither user-defined material subroutines nor user-defined elements were used in this work. All the constitutive equations are available in the ABAQUS material library. In addition, the ply strengths calculated in this work have been determined using the same set of micromechanical parameters.

The model was able to reproduce the stress-strain curves (without fitting parameters), as well as the deformation and fracture mechanisms experimentally observed. In particular, the simulations of the compression tests reproduced the plastic microbuckling, while the simulations of the tensile test reproduced the fiber breakage process according to the a Weibull distribution drawn from experimental data.

The results summarized in this work suggest the possibility of replacing (at least partially) the physical characterization tests by virtual ones, based on a complete characterization of the microconstituents. These virtual tests provide full control of the composite microstructure and constituent properties. Moreover, very complex stress states and parametric studies can be performed to optimize the composite properties. Therefore, the obtained properties might be used in mesomechanical models instead of experimental ones in order to predict laminate properties (multi-scale strategy).

All the simulations were carried out using an standard Intel core i7 CPU requiring computational times ranging under one hour. As a consequence, this methodology provides an affordable way to predict stiffness and strength of a UD FRP ply.

Extending this methodology beyond the strength and stiffness determination will be a priority in the near future. So far, preliminary models have been tested in order to determine not only the strength, which can be considered as a ply damage initiation threshold, but also the fracture toughness leading to the UD ply damage propagation study. Taken advantage of the increasing computational resources, detailed FE models reproducing complex loading states turned to be feasible [5], leading computational micromechanics to be a reliable and convenient resource to be taken into account as a UD FRP ply property predictive method .

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